

Analysis of Land Use/Land Cover Changes and Their Impacts on Land Surface Temperature Variation in Kisangani City (DRC)

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Abstract

Uncontrolled urbanization in developing countries exerts profound impacts on local microclimates, thereby contributing to climate change processes at both local and regional scales. In this study, remote sensing techniques were employed to quantify land use/land cover (LULC) dynamics and to assess their effects on land surface temperature (LST) variations in Kisangani, Democratic Republic of the Congo, over the period 2014–2024. The LULC change analysis revealed a marked increase in built-up and bare land areas (+86.43%) and, to a lesser extent, in fallows/croplands (+5.56%), accompanied by a substantial decline in primary forest cover (–22.96%). These structural transformations in land cover were strongly associated with a significant rise in LST. Overall, the progressive conversion of vegetated surfaces into impervious and bare land contributed to an average LST increase of +4.2 °C over the ten-year period, thereby evidencing the direct influence of urbanization on local warming processes.

Keywords : Urbanization, Land Surface Temperature, Land Use/Land Cover Change, Urban Planning, Kisangani.

1. Introduction

Population growth exerts strong pressure on natural resources, often driving their overexploitation (Imbernon 2000; Dimnwobi et al. 2021; Bologna & Aquino 2020; Bajja et al.

2024; Osman et al. 2025). According to the United Nations, the global population, currently estimated at 7.3 billion, could reach 9.7 billion by 2050, with nearly two-thirds concentrated in urban areas (Emilie 2017). Although cities occupy less than 3% of the Earth's terrestrial surface, they generate distinct thermal signatures, expressed through urban heat islands (UHIs), as well as chemical signatures such as elevated greenhouse gas emissions (Emilie 2017; Zhou et al. 2022).

Urban expansion frequently results in profound land cover transformations, notably deforestation and the conversion of primary forests into agricultural or peri-urban land, reflecting the direct response to increasing resource demand from rapidly growing populations (Maréchal 2012). These land use/land cover (LULC) changes alter surface energy balances, increase land surface temperature (LST), and intensify UHIs, which are characterized by a persistent positive temperature anomaly between urban cores and surrounding rural environments (Maheng et al. 2024; Makaya et al. 2025; Halefom et al. 2024; Roba et al. 2024). The amplification of UHIs is further associated with higher levels of atmospheric pollution, increased energy demand, and multiple risks to human health and well-being (Kumar et al. 2002; Islam et al. 2024; Yu et al. 2024).

At a global scale, the observed increase in average surface temperatures since the early 20th century has placed climate change at the forefront of environmental concerns (Gordana et al. 2018). Within this context, UHIs are considered a critical urban phenomenon requiring urgent mitigation (Xavier 2015). Empirical studies have demonstrated that LST dynamics in urban environments are strongly modulated by the degree of urbanization (Liyang 2022), and that the UHI effect can be evaluated by comparing LST differences between urban and rural zones (Xavier 2015).

Remote sensing in the thermal infrared domain provides a robust framework for assessing LST variations with high spatial and temporal consistency (Ouyang et al. 2024; Zheng et al. 2024). Thermal infrared imagery enables quantification of radiative heat fluxes at the Earth's surface, allowing precise mapping of temperature gradients at both local and regional scales (Dominique 2022).

In the African context, the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) is among the countries experiencing rapid, poorly regulated urbanization. This situation stems from the dual effect of sustained population growth and weak institutional coordination in urban planning, generating

substantial environmental pressures and long-lasting alterations of natural ecosystems (Opelele et al. 2021). Kisangani, one of the country's largest urban centers, has undergone accelerated demographic growth over the past decade, fueling unplanned urban sprawl. This expansion has triggered significant land cover conversions, intensifying the demand for natural resources and modifying local thermal regimes. These dynamics are reflected in uncontrolled construction, the proliferation of cleared land, and pronounced shifts in LST patterns, thereby raising critical challenges for sustainable land management and ecological resilience (Maréchal 2012).

Despite increasing recognition of the adverse impacts of unregulated urbanization on microclimatic conditions, empirical studies examining the direct relationship between LULC dynamics and LST variation remain scarce in tropical developing cities, particularly in Kisangani. This research gap limits understanding of the coupled effects of urban expansion and deforestation on local climate systems. To address this gap, the present study investigates the impacts of LULC changes on LST variation in Kisangani between 2014 and 2024. Specifically, it aims to (i) quantify LULC transitions over the ten-year period and (ii) assess their influence on surface temperature dynamics. By doing so, this study provides critical insights into the interactions among urbanization, land cover change, and microclimate, thereby contributing to knowledge essential for informed urban planning and climate adaptation strategies in rapidly urbanizing tropical landscapes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

This study was conducted in Kisangani, the capital city of Tshopo Province in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) (Fig. 1). The urban area extends across both banks of the Congo River, comprising five municipalities on the right bank, one municipality on the left bank, and the peri-urban community of Lubuya-Bera. Geographically, Kisangani is situated near the equator ($0^{\circ}31' N$; $25^{\circ}11' E$) and covers an estimated surface area of approximately 2,699 km² (Administrative Annual Report of the Territory, 2022). The city lies at a mean elevation of 396 m, with altitudes ranging from 376 m to 450 m.

From a climatic perspective, Kisangani belongs to the equatorial hot and humid tropical domain, classified as "Af" under Köppen's system. The region experiences relatively stable thermal conditions with an annual mean temperature of $\sim 25^{\circ}C$, coupled with high and evenly distributed rainfall averaging 1,748 mm per year (Nshimba 2008; Angoyo et al. 2017). The city

is part of the Congo River Basin and is intersected by multiple rivers, notably the Tshopo and Lindi, both important tributaries of the Congo River, which contribute to local hydrological dynamics.

The prevailing soils are Oxisols, characterized by advanced weathering, low organic matter content, and enrichment in iron and aluminum sesquioxides. Their texture is predominantly clay-sandy, with low natural fertility and high susceptibility to leaching (Maréchal 2012; Mikwa 2012).

Vegetation belongs to the central forest sector of the Guineo-Congolian phytogeographical region. It is dominated by humid dense forests interspersed with secondary vegetation resulting from anthropogenic disturbances. The landscape is primarily composed of young secondary forests, forest regrowth areas, swamp forests, and fragmented patches of relic primary forest (Angoyo et al. 2017).

Fig 1. Study area: (a) Kisangani town. (b) Kisangani town in the DRC and (c) DRC in Africa.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Satellite Image Acquisition

This study examined the spatio-temporal evolution of land use/land cover (LULC) and its impacts on land surface temperature (LST) dynamics in Kisangani over the period 2014–2024. The analysis was conducted using multispectral satellite data from the Landsat program, which provides a consistent and long-term observational record suitable for monitoring environmental change at decadal scales. Two reference years, 2014 and 2024, were selected to capture a ten-year interval, enabling the assessment of major LULC transitions and their associated thermal effects.

Satellite imagery was acquired from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer platform (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). The study area is encompassed by Path 176 and Rows 059 and 060 of the Worldwide Reference System (WRS-2). The datasets included Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager/Thermal Infrared Sensor (OLI/TIRS) images for both reference years. These datasets integrate visible, near-infrared, shortwave infrared, and thermal infrared bands, which are essential for LULC classification as well as for the retrieval of LST through radiometric and atmospheric correction procedures.

The technical characteristics of the selected imagery, including acquisition date, spatial resolution, spectral configuration, radiometric properties, and processing level, are summarized in Table 1. This information provides the basis for ensuring the reliability and comparability of results across the two temporal benchmarks.

Table 1. Description of the Landsat Satellite Dataset Used in the Study

Acquisition date	Sensor	Band name	Wayelength (μm)	Description	Spatial resolution
March 15. 2014	Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS	Band 1	0.43-0.45	Coastal aerosol	30 m x 30 m
		Band 2	0.45-0.51	Blue	30 m x 30 m
		Band 3	0.53-0.59	Green	30 m x 30 m
		Band 4	0.64-0.67	Red	30 m x 30 m
		Band 5	0.85-0.88	Near-Infrared(NIR)	30 m x 30 m

& March 18 . 2024	Band 6	1.57-1.65	Shortwave Infrared 1 (SWIR 1)	30 m x 30 m
	Band 7	2.11-2.29	ShortwaveInfrared 2 (SWIR 2)	30 m x 30 m
	Band 8	0.52-0.90	Panchromatic	15 m x15 m
	Band 9	1.36-1.38	Cirrus	15 m x15 m
	Band 10	10.60-11.19	Thermal infrared 1	30 m x 30 m
	Band 11	11.50-12.51	Thermal infrared 2	30 m x 30 m

2.2.2. Preprocessing

The acquired Landsat images were subjected to standard preprocessing procedures to enhance their radiometric quality and minimize atmospheric distortions. Using ArcGIS 10.5 and ENVI 5.3, raw scenes were first mosaicked and then corrected radiometrically to convert digital numbers into physically meaningful values, followed by atmospheric correction with the FLAASH algorithm to mitigate scattering and absorption effects and standardize surface reflectance. False-color composites were subsequently generated to facilitate visual interpretation of land cover: for Landsat 7 ETM+, bands 3 (Red), 4 (NIR), and 5 (SWIR1) were combined, while for Landsat 8 OLI, bands 4 (Red), 5 (NIR), and 6 (SWIR1) were used. Finally, a mask was applied to exclude non-relevant features (e.g., clouds, shadows, and areas outside the study boundary), ensuring consistency and reliability for subsequent land cover classification and temperature analysis.

2.2.3. Image Classification

The second phase of the study consisted of performing supervised classification of the images (Fotsing 1998, Sitayeb & Benabdeli 2008, Barima et al. 2010, Zhao et al. 2023, Fayaz et al. 2024, Perez-Guerra et al. 2023), a widely used remote sensing method for extracting detailed land cover information. This approach relies on the use of training samples to guide the classification algorithm in assigning pixels to predefined classes (Momo Solefack et al. 2013, Nasiri et al. 2022, Nivedita et al. 2018). Training samples generally consist of pixels whose class membership is already known, thereby allowing the algorithm to learn the spectral characteristics of each class. Once trained, the algorithm is applied to the entire image, assigning each pixel to a class based on its spectral properties.

For this study, the maximum likelihood classifier was employed. This algorithm is based on the probability that a given pixel belongs to a specific class according to its spectral properties (Eugène & Parfait 2021). It evaluates the likelihood that a pixel's observed values originate from the spectral distributions of each class and assigns the pixel to the class with the highest probability. In other words, the algorithm maximizes the likelihood of the observed data given the predefined classes.

The definition of land cover classes was based on spectral analysis of satellite images, including color composites and spectral profile examination (Bickel et al. 2006). Based on this analysis, four land cover classes were identified in the study area : primary forest, built-up/bare soil mosaic, secondary forest–fallow–cropland mosaic, and water bodies.

2.2.4. Classification Accuracy Assessment

In this study, the accuracy of the supervised classification was evaluated using a confusion matrix (Godard 2005). This matrix is constructed by comparing classified data with reference data. By cross-tabulating reference data (rows) and classification results (columns), it enables estimation of classification quality using the following parameters (Duminil 2007) :

- ❖ **Overall Accuracy** : the ratio of correctly classified pixels (corresponding to the diagonal of the confusion matrix) to the total number of reference pixels.
- ❖ **User's Accuracy (UA)** : the proportion of pixels assigned to a given class in the classification that actually belong to that class in the reference data, providing a measure of reliability for each class.
- ❖ **Producer's Accuracy (PA)** : the proportion of reference pixels of a given class correctly assigned by the classification, providing a measure of how well the classification represents each class.
- ❖ **Kappa Coefficient** : an index expressing the proportional reduction in error achieved by the classification compared to a completely random classification. Kappa values range from 0 to 1. Its formula is given by Pontius (2000) :

$$K = \frac{P_o - P_c}{1 - P_c} \quad (1)$$

Where P_o is the observed proportion of correctly classified elements and P_c is the expected proportion of correctly classified elements by chance.

2.2.5. Assessment of Land Use/Land Cover Changes

The transition matrix is a commonly used analytical method to quantify and represent class changes within a system over a given period. It takes the form of a square matrix in which each cell indicates the transition of elements from one land cover class to another. In this study, a transition matrix was generated to compare land cover between 2014 and 2024. This matrix allowed precise evaluation of land cover dynamics, particularly the reduction of forest areas and the expansion of urban zones during the study period.

To statistically analyze LULC changes in Kisangani between 2014 and 2024, two parameters were computed : area statistics and rate of change of land cover classes. The LULC change analysis was performed by comparing the areal extents of land cover classes in 2014 and 2024. Areas were calculated from the attribute tables of the classified images using the “Calculate Geometry” tool in ArcGIS 10.5. For annual rates of spatial expansion, the standardized formula proposed by Puyravaud (2002) was adopted.

2.2.6. Impact of Land Use/Land Cover Changes on Surface Temperature Variation

2.2.6.1. Land Surface Temperature (LST) Estimation

The study utilized the thermal infrared bands of the Landsat images following the approach established by Qin et al. (2001) to derive LST. The retrieval procedure involved four main steps :

1° Conversion of Digital Numbers (DN) to Spectral Radiance (L_λ):

Thermal bands (Band 6 for Landsat 7 and Band 10 for Landsat 8) were used to convert DN values into spectral radiance using the following formula (Mumtaz et al. 2020) :

$$L_\lambda = \left(\frac{L_{MAX} - L_{MIN}}{QCAL_{MAX} - QCAL_{MIN}} \right) X (QCAL - QCAL_{MIN}) + L_{MIN} \quad (2)$$

Where L_{MAX} = maximum spectral radiance (15.600 for TM),

L_{MIN} = minimum spectral radiance (1.238 for TM),

$QCAL_{MAX}$ = valeur numérique maximale (DN) (255).

$QCAL_{MIN}$ = maximum DN value (255),

$QCAL$ = DN value of the thermal band.

These parameters were extracted from the metadata files of each Landsat image

2°) Conversion of Spectral Radiance to Brightness Temperature (TB)

Brightness temperature (in Kelvin) was computed as:

$$T_B = \frac{K_2}{\ln\left(\frac{K_1}{L_\lambda} + 1\right)} \quad (3)$$

Where T_B = satellite brightness temperature (K),

L_λ = spectral radiance,

K_1 et K_2 = sensor calibration constants.

For Landsat-8 OLI, $K_1 = 774.89$ and $K_2 = 1\,321.08$ (Ihlen 2019).

3°) Land Surface Temperature (LST) Retrieval:

The brightness temperature obtained, also referred to as blackbody temperature, required further correction for spectral emissivity (ϵ). The corrected LST was computed following Artis & Carnahan's (1982) algorithm :

$$S_T = \frac{T_B}{1 + \left(\frac{\lambda T_B}{\rho}\right) \ln \epsilon} - 273,15 \quad (4)$$

Where S_T = land surface temperature (°C),

T_B = brightness temperature (K),

$\lambda = 11.5 \mu\text{m}$ (emitted wavelength) ,

$\rho = 1.438 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mK}$.

ϵ = emissivity (ranging from 0.97 to 0.99).

Emissivity was estimated using vegetation proportion (P_v), derived from NDVI values, according to :

$$\epsilon = 0,004P_v + 0,986 \quad (5)$$

$$P_v = \left(\frac{NDVI - NDVI_{min}}{NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min}} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

$$NDVI = \frac{PIR - Rouge}{PIR + Rouge} \quad (7)$$

Where NDVI, $NDVI_{min}$ and $NDVI_{max}$ respectively represent the per-pixel value of NDVI, NDVI minimum and maximum NDVI.

2.2.6.2. Impact of Land Use/Land Cover Changes on LST Variations

To assess the impact of land use/land cover (LULC) changes on land surface temperature (LST) variations in Kisangani, it is essential to analyze the thermal signatures of these changes using spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (Imran et al., 2021). To achieve this, the study employed randomly distributed sampling points across different land cover classes, enabling the comparison of the relationship between LST and NDVI through specific measurements.

LST and NDVI values were collected at 30 randomly selected sampling points within the different LULC classes. A statistical analysis was then performed to evaluate the correlations between surface temperature variations (LST) and the vegetation index (NDVI), which reflect the condition and dynamics of land cover. Pearson's correlation test was applied to quantify the strength and direction of the relationship between these two variables.

Additionally, a zonal statistical analysis was conducted. This method extracts relevant information on the mean surface temperature by land cover class through the overlay of land use and LST layers. First, the vector layer representing land cover and the raster layer of LST for the study area were imported into ArcGIS. The vector layer was then prepared by applying attribute table operations to define the analysis zones. To compute zonal statistics, the "Zonal Statistics as Table" tool in ArcGIS was employed, which calculates statistical measures (such as mean values) of LST for each land cover class. This approach allowed us to accurately quantify LST variations according to different land use/land cover categories.

3. Results

3.1. Accuracy Assessment of Classification

Confusion matrices generated from the Maximum Likelihood classification method (Table 2) were used to evaluate classification performance. Results indicate that the overall classification accuracy exceeded 90%, with a Kappa coefficient greater than 0.9, demonstrating a strong agreement between predicted and reference classes. Furthermore, both producer's and user's accuracies exceeded 70%, reflecting an acceptable quality of classification across all LULC classes.

Table 2. Classification Accuracy Assessment

LULC Classes	2014		2024	
	PA	UA	PA	UA
	(%)		(%)	
Primary forest	99.26	99.96	96.83	99.92
Fallow and cropland	100	71.33	99.38	90.7
Built-up and bare soil	100	96.01	100	94.08
Water	99.03	100	99.14	100
Overall accuracy	99.257	98.148		
Kappa coefficient	0.978	0.972		

3.2. Land Use/Land Cover Change Mapping from 2014 to 2024

Figure 2 illustrates the LULC maps of Kisangani for 2014 and 2024. Statistics related to the different LULC classes and their rates of change are summarized in Table 3.

In 2014, the LULC distribution of Kisangani was dominated by primary forest, covering 978.51 km² (44.6% of the total area). Secondary forest/fallow and cropland also occupied a large portion of the territory, representing 43.34% (950.87 km²). In contrast, built-up and bare soil areas covered 198.36 km² (9.04%), while water bodies accounted for 66.18 km² (3.016%).

By 2024, LULC changes were more pronounced. Primary forest cover decreased substantially to 753.82 km² (34.37% of the total area). Secondary forest/fallow and cropland remained predominant, covering 45.74% (1003.75 km²). Built-up and bare soil areas, however, increased significantly to 369.81 km² (16.86%). Water bodies remained marginal, covering 66.59 km² (3.04%).

Between 2014 and 2024, primary forest lost 224.69 km², corresponding to a decline of 2.61%. Built-up/bare soil areas gained 259.99 km², equivalent to a 6.23% increase. Secondary forest/fallow and cropland also experienced notable changes, gaining 52.88 km² (0.54%). Water bodies slightly increased by 0.41 km² (0.06%).

Fig 2. Land use/land cover (LULC) maps of Kisangani for 2014 and 2024

Table 3. Areas of LULC classes and their annual rate of change

LULC Classes	Area (Km ²)		Annual rate of change (2014–2024) (%)
	2014	2024	
Primary forest	978.51	753.82	-2.61
Fallow and cropland	950.87	1003.75	0.54
Built-up and bare soil	198.36	369.81	6.23
Water bodies	66.18	66.59	0.06

3.3. Land use/land cover change mapping in Kisangani from 2014 to 2024

Table 4 presents the land use/land cover (LULC) transitions for each class between 2014 and 2024 in Kisangani. The results show that 48.54 km², 211.43 km², and 0.09 km² of forest were converted into built-up/bare soil areas, secondary forest/fallow and cropland, and water bodies, respectively. Similarly, 30.88 km², 178.97 km², and 0.06 km² of secondary forest/fallow and cropland were transformed into forest, built-up/bare soil areas, and water bodies, respectively.

The surface occupied by built-up and bare soil areas has experienced a significant expansion across Kisangani. The land use transitions reveal that most of the secondary forest/fallow and cropland (178.97 km²) were converted into built-up/bare soil, while a large portion of the primary forest (211.43 km²) was transformed into secondary forest/fallow and cropland. These transformations illustrate both the growing urbanization and the intensification of agricultural activities occurring at the expense of forested areas.

Table 4. Transition matrix between 2014 and 2024

		2014				
2024	Classe LULC	Primary forest	Built-up and bare soil	Fallow and cropland	Water	Total 2024
	Primary forest	718.20	4.08	30.88	0.45	753.82
	Built-up and bare soil	48.54	140.52	178.97	1.75	369.81
	Fallow and cropland	211.43	51.71	740.27	0.18	1003.75
	Water	0.09	2.03	0.06	63.78	66.59
Total 2014		1098.60	109.82	920.08	65.69	

3.4. Variations in Land Surface Temperature (LST)

Figure 3 illustrates the spatial distribution of land surface temperature (LST) and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) for Kisangani in 2014 and 2024. The results show that, in 2014, the minimum and maximum LST values were 19.48°C and 31.21°C, respectively. The NDVI ranged from -0.12 to 0.61, with a mean value of 0.43.

In 2024, the minimum and maximum LST values increased to 22.05°C and 36.83°C, respectively. Regarding NDVI, values ranged from -0.17 to 0.61, with a mean value of 0.41.

Between 2014 and 2024, the observed variations in LST and NDVI indicate a pronounced trend. LST exhibited a clear upward tendency, with minimum temperatures increasing from 19.48°C in 2014 to 22.05°C in 2024, while maximum temperatures rose from 31.21°C in 2014 to 36.83°C in 2024. Although NDVI registered a slight decline, it still indicates the persistence of vegetative cover, albeit under progressive regression over time.

Regarding the mean land surface temperature, the findings indicate a clear increasing trend over the study period, as the average surface temperature rose from 23.16°C in 2014 to 27.36°C in 2024.

Fig 3. LST and NDVI maps of Kisangani for 2014 and 2024

3.5. Variation in Land Surface Temperature across Land Use/Land Cover Classes

Land surface temperatures (LST), derived from Landsat imagery, reveal a clear gradient across different land use/land cover (LULC) classes—namely built-up/bare soil, secondary forest/fallow and cropland, water bodies, and primary forest—during the period 2014–2024. These findings support the hypothesis that the urban expansion observed over the past decade has significantly contributed to the rise in LST.

Table 5. Variation in LST across LULC classes

LULC Classes	Land surface temperature (°C)	
	2014	2024
Primary forest	22.88	26.50
Fallow and cropland	23.26	27.43
Built-up and bare soil	24.64	29.35
Water	21.33	24.82

The mean LST values for each land cover class are presented in Table 5. In 2014, built-up and bare soil areas exhibited the highest mean surface temperature (24.64 °C), which rose to 29.35 °C by 2024. The lowest values were recorded in primary forest and water bodies, with respective averages of 22.88 °C and 21.33 °C in 2014, and 26.50 °C and 24.82 °C in 2024.

3.6. Relationship between NDVI and Land Surface Temperature

To investigate the relationship between NDVI and LST in Kisangani, multiple sampling points were used to compare this relationship for 2014 and 2024. The results are illustrated in **Fig. 4**. Correlation and regression analyses were performed, with LST as the dependent variable and NDVI as the independent variable. Pearson’s correlation test revealed a strong inverse relationship between LST and NDVI, confirming that higher temperatures are associated with areas of reduced vegetation cover. The Pearson correlation coefficients were –0.86 in 2014 and –0.72 in 2024.

Fig 4. Relationships between NDVI and LST of Kisangani in 2014 and 2024

Linear regression analyses further demonstrate the negative correlation between LST and NDVI. Areas with sparse vegetation, indicated by low NDVI values, correspond to significantly higher LST, whereas areas with dense vegetation cover (high NDVI values) exhibit lower surface temperatures.

4. Discussion

The analysis of land use/land cover dynamics in Kisangani between 2014 and 2024 highlights a marked transformation of the landscape, characterized by a substantial increase in built-up and bare soil areas (+259.99 km²) and a notable decline in primary forest (-344.78 km²). This trend reflects a rapid urbanization process, comparable to that documented in

Yaoundé (Fopa, 2019), and can be directly linked to the strong demographic growth recorded over the past decade. These findings align with those of Darren et al. (2021), who emphasize the role of anthropogenic pressure in driving the conversion of natural landscapes into artificial environments in African metropolitan areas.

The impact of these land use changes on LST reveals a progressive increase in minimum, mean, and maximum surface temperatures across Kisangani between 2004 and 2024. Over this period, minimum, mean, and maximum LST values rose by 8.49 °C, 8.14 °C, and 3.81 °C, respectively. While these variations are strongly associated with land use changes, they may also reflect the influence of global climate warming, which extends beyond the scope of this study. The upward trend observed across all land cover classes, including forest and water, reinforces this hypothesis.

The expansion of built-up and bare soil surfaces emerges as a primary driver of LST elevation in Kisangani. The conversion of natural landscapes into impervious surfaces with reduced evapotranspiration promotes solar heat storage and re-radiation, thereby intensifying surface urban heat islands (Swades & Ziaul, 2017; Opelele, 2021). To refine this analysis, two complementary approaches were employed: (i) zonal statistics integrating LULC classes with LST to assess thermal variations by cover type, and (ii) correlation analyses between LST and NDVI as a biophysical indicator of vegetation density (Mamadou et al., 2021; Guechi et al., 2022; Manal et al., 2021).

Results indicate that built-up and bare soil areas record the highest LST, followed by fallow and cropland, while forests and water bodies display significantly lower values. Over the study period, mean LST increased by 8.38 °C in built-up/bare soil areas, 7.54 °C in forests, 8.13 °C in fallow/cropland, and 5.83 °C in water bodies. This spatial distribution confirms the mitigating effect of vegetation and water on surface temperature, in agreement with previous studies by Bayes et al. (2013) and Darren et al. (2021). The NDVI–LST correlation further underscores the inverse relationship, highlighting vegetation density as a key factor in thermal regulation, consistent with the findings of Swades & Ziaul (2017).

5. Conclusion

This study provided a quantitative and spatial assessment of the impact of land use/land cover changes on land surface temperature dynamics in Kisangani between 2014 and 2024, using Landsat imagery. The findings revealed a pronounced conversion of primary forest into built-up, bare soil, and agricultural land, resulting in a significant increase in mean LST—from 23.16 °C to 27.36 °C over a decade. Built-up and bare soil surfaces were the most thermally impacted, reaching 36.82 °C in 2024, thereby confirming their dominant role in amplifying surface urban heat islands.

Statistical analyses demonstrated a robust negative correlation between LST and NDVI, indicating that vegetation density acts as a natural thermal regulator through evapotranspiration and moisture retention. This underscores the ecological and climatic importance of urban and peri-urban green spaces in mitigating the impacts of rapid urbanization on the local microclimate.

The results highlight the relevance of combining Landsat data with biophysical indices to better understand the interactions between land use dynamics and thermal variations in humid tropical environments. Moreover, they provide a sound basis for modeling future urbanization scenarios and their potential local climatic impacts.

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